

Factors Mitigating Treatment Outcomes and Treatment Outcomes for Teens Suffering from Anxiety Disorders

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Abstract

This article explores outcomes treatment and factors that mitigate treatment outcomes for youth suffering from anxiety disorders. It places a special emphasis on randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of any psychological therapy (i.e., not just CBT-based methods) using any form of delivery (including cCBT) for anxiety disorders among adolescents. According to the American Psychological Association (2002), the average age at which external manifestations of adolescence becomes clear is 11 years, the legal age of adulthood in most countries, and the age at which child and adolescent mental health services end is eighteen. The age range was determined to be 11-18 years (inclusive), and we based this on the fact that eleven was the average age at which these indicators became clear. In addition, the age range of young people attending secondary school is normally between 11 and 18; Therefore, adolescents in this age range have comparable educational and social needs and duties (Perry et al., 1993). Depression, anxiety, and somatoform disorders are all examples of what are called affective disorders or EDs (National Institute for Health and

Clinical Excellence NICE, 2011). According to the Globe Health Organization (WHO, 2017), these are the most common mental illnesses worldwide, and public health systems have recorded an alarming increase in the incidence of these conditions in recent years (Chisholm et al., 2016).). According to the findings of several scientific studies, the most effective therapy for EDs appears to be psychological treatments (Hollon et al., 2006; Joesch et al., 2011; National Institute of Health and Clinical Excellence NICE, 2011, Watts et al. , 2015). Although medication is needed for severe cases, it is often unnecessary in people with mild to moderate symptoms (Dunlop et al., 2019). In fact, research has shown that patients who receive psychotherapy have a much higher chance of a full recovery (Wells et al., 2000). Individual and group psychological therapies have traditionally been two of the most common methods used to treat EDs; however, there is no clear consensus as to whether there is a difference in their achievements between the two.

Keywords: *Youth Suffering from Anxiety Disorders, Psychological Treatment Outcomes, Factors Mitigating Psychological Treatment Outcomes, Anxiety Disorders, Psychological Treatment, Clinical Psychology*

1. Introduction

More research on short transdiagnostic treatments is needed because of the importance of implementing evidence-supported interventions (Moriani et al. 2017, Gálvez-Lara et al., 2018; Gálvez-Lara et al., 2019a); this is because of the importance of implementing evidence-based interventions. (“Brief psychological treatments for emotional disorders in Primary and ...”) Considering this, the aim of this study is to decide whether there is a significant difference between the effects of short-term individual and short group psychotherapies on EDs and interventions based on psychopharmacology. It was assumed that patients given either of the two short types of psychotherapy would have better clinical outcomes than patients given psychotropic drugs. On the one hand, they will experience a greater reduction in the severity of their ED symptoms, and on the other hand, they will experience a greater elimination of their diagnosis for various disorders. In addition, it has been hypothesized that patients taking part in short-term individual

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psychotherapy will experience better clinical outcomes (in terms of severity of their symptoms and loss of diagnosis) than those who take part in brief group psychotherapy.

- (i) *The effects of psychological treatments on reducing anxiety disorder symptoms and*
- (ii) *Its effectiveness in achieving remission from the underlying anxiety disorder is being evaluated.*
- (iii) *therapies in the treatment of anxiety disorders in adolescents vary depending on the following treatment and demographic variables.*

Cognitive behavioral therapy (including cCBT) versus non-CBT intervention; mode of treatment (individual, group, mixed group and individual, cCBT).

- *Age.*
- *Number of treatments hours.*
- *Disorder-specific and general anxiety treatment.*
- *Active and passive control group; clinical and community sample.*
- *primary anxiety disorder.*
- *Ethnicity.*

In this context, some studies claim that the individual method is more effective than the group approach (Gili et al. 2014, Hauksson et al., 2017, Moreno et al., 2013), but other studies conclude that both. The approaches are equally effective (Cuijpers et al. 2008, Fawcett et al., 2019, Huntley et al., 2012, Neufeld et al., 2020, van Rijn and Wild, 2016). (“Brief psychological treatments for emotional disorders in Primary and ...”) On the other hand, most of the primary care (PC) patients are treated only with drugs that pose a potential risk to their health (Bebbington et al. 2000). In addition, adherence to psychological manual treatments tends to be weak and incomplete, even when patients are referred to exceptional care. This is the case regardless of whether the patient receives exceptional care (Gyani et al. 2015, Labrador et al. 2011).

Therefore, "brief psychotherapies" have appeared as a potential treatment for eating disorders, especially for individuals who only show mild to moderate symptoms (Shepardson et al. 2016). According to the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by Cape et al. (2010), these treatments

should have more than two or less than ten sessions to help alleviate ED symptoms (Bernhardsdottir et al. 2013, Koutra et al. 2010, Saravanan et al. 2017).). Several studies have shown that conventional treatments and short treatments have comparable results (Miller, 2000, Nieuwsma et al. 2012). In addition, the use of time as a tool in developing a therapeutic relationship appears to be what makes brief psychotherapies more effective in improving adherence to treatment (Bedics et al. 2005, Fosha, 2004). Due to the high rate of comorbidities available in emergency departments (González-Robles, Dáz-Garca, Miguel, Garca-Palacios, & Botella, 2018), transdiagnostic techniques have been set up to treat them simultaneously (Barlow et al. 2017). , Şakiris and Berle, 2019). In fact, it has been shown that most affective disorders have some basic features (McManus et al. 2011, Pascual-Vera et al. 2019). In this context, the Unified Protocol for Emergency Services is accepted as one of the most important transdiagnostic treatment guidelines (Barlow et al. 2014). It has been well used in both individual (Barlow et al. 2017) and group settings (Bullis et al., 2015, Osma et al., 2018), respectively. (“Brief psychological treatments for emotional disorders in Primary and ...”) It has been shown in several studies to be beneficial in alleviating anxious and depressive symptoms in individuals suffering from comorbid conditions (McManus et al. 2011, Norton, 2008; Sakiris and Berle, 2019). In addition, not so long ago Cassiello-Robins et al. (2020) implies that an adapted version of the Unified Protocol could be implemented in a condensed form.

1. Psychoeducation and Other Issues

- *The first impetus to make a change. Decision-making balancing approaches are used to define therapeutic goals and increase patient adherence to treatment.*
- *Psychoeducation is about emotions. The adaptive role of emotions as well as the concept of "emotion-based behaviors" are presented here.*
- *Emotion awareness training. It is taught and practiced having emotional awareness centered in the present without judgment.*
- *Rearrangement of mental processes Irrational ways of thinking can be found and changed through the application of various strategies.*

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- *Adjust your avoidance behaviors as needed. To change avoidance behaviors, it is first necessary to understand the role those avoidant behaviors play in the development and maintenance of EDs.*
- *Raise your threshold for the various sensations your body experiences. In this section, various exercises that create sensations in the body are performed and analyzed.*
- *Emotional exposure. Patients should be encouraged to face the triggers of their symptoms to develop an emotional habit.*
- *Relapse prevention. Learned skills are reviewed and instructions are given to deal with future scenarios.*
- *An intensified group psychotherapy. Experimental group in the context of a group setting of about ten participants, where patients received the same intervention as outlined in the earlier section... It was presented by clinical psychologists in the psychotherapy and counseling clinics of Cordoba (Spain).*

In psychology, research often focuses on deciding whether a treatment is successful using a variety of patient-reported outcome measures (Neale & Strang, 2015). Researchers do not often look at what effect interventions really have on an outcome. The "how" question is mediation research that looks to understand the processes that produce results and the mechanisms involved in these processes.

Mediation is claimed to occur when the effect of one variable, mostly an intervention, has an impact on an outcome through a change in the behavior of a third variable. The name given to this third variable is the tool. The processes by which a therapy exerts its effects can also be called mediators of these effects.

2. Advancement of Clinical Practice

Both the development of psychological theory and the development of clinical practice are important reasons why the study of mediation is so important. The search for psychological mediators can supply an opportunity to tap into the important processes involved in producing

positive outcomes. This editorial attempt to supply a basic understanding of mediation, to give an idea of its scope, and to explain that although this type of analysis may need some professional knowledge, it is essential to improve our understanding of psychiatric treatments. A critical review of current research from psychological intervention studies to mediation processes is supplied to illustrate the importance and value of mediation work, as well as the potential limitations that may arise in such an analysis. These studies come from psychological intervention research.

Randomized controlled trials, commonly known as RCTs, are widely accepted as the best method for evaluating improvement in treatment (Evans, 2003). Also, RCTs are the most effective type of research design for deciding whether mediation exists. When researchers use randomization, they may assume that there are no variables confounding the relationship between intervention and mediator and the relationship between intervention and outcome. (“Establishing how psychological therapies work: the importance of ...”) Because the mediator is not typically randomized, this design does not exclude the possibility that there may be unmeasured variables that confuse the relationship between mediator and outcome (MacKinnon & Pirlott, 2015). Further discussion of confounding factors can be found in the section below.

In a perfect world, the design phase for RCTs would include brokerage analysis as a core part of the overall design process. This will involve including mechanism measures in addition to outcome measures and considering the need for how many times and at what time points these are examined. Variables to be included in the mediation analysis should be informed by theory and/or empirical research to prevent negativities that may hinder theoretical understanding (Johansson & Hogland, 2007) .

3. How Does the Consultation Process Start?

As a result of the increasing number of citations to Baron and Kenny's landmark paper, first published in 1986, there is a growing body of work in psychology devoted to mediation work (Baron & Kenny, 1986). Baron and Kenny's article discusses mediation using a model with three different variable paths. The following are three variables:

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According to the approach developed by Baron and Kenny, some regressions are needed to decide the statistical significance of correlations that exist between variables on various routes. The purpose of the regression series is to extract the mechanical process of M by deciding whether the following four conditions are met:

- (1) In the regression of Y on R (path c), the effect of the intervention variable was statistically significant.*
- (2) In a regression of Mover R (path a), the effect of the intervention variable is statistically significant. (“Establishing how psychological therapies work: the importance of...”)*
- (3) In a regression of Y on R (path c') and M (path b), the effect of the go-between*

regression (3), the effect of the intervention is reduced to zero, which is often referred to as "full mediation". The causal stage approach to mediation is one of the names sometimes given to this technique (MacKinnon et al. 2002, 2007).

There are limitations mentioned elsewhere in connection with this evaluation of the counseling mechanism/mediation. Although this method of assessing mediation is now common in published research, there are some of these disadvantages (Emsley et al. 2010; Kazdin, 2007; MacKinnon et al., 2002; Zhao et al., 2010). . The requirement for a strong intervention effect is one of the problems associated with the approach, as noted above. We disagree with those who say that mediation should only be discovered when it has a major intervention effect (Emsley et al. 2010; MacKinnon, 2008), and we feel the same way. Where this is not the case, mediation training may be even more important. This allows researchers to decide whether the intervention has the desired effect on the mediator, whether the mediator influences the outcome, or whether there is evidence of suppression (MacKinnon et al. 2000; MacKinnon, 2008). When indirect and direct effects work against each other, a phenomenon known as suppression occurs.

One of the disadvantages of the causal stages approach is that it does not explicitly measure the indirect effect resulting from the mediator. Alternatively, it makes inferences about mediation based on the results of many hypothesis tests. Moreover, the power of this approach to detect mediated effects has been shown to be weak. In other words, researchers using this strategy risk

losing the effects even while they are there (Hayes, 2009; MacKinnon et al. 2002, 2007; Preacher & Hayes, 2008). Finally, Baron and Kenny did not consider the possibility of skewed findings caused by unmeasured confounding factors. These are variables that have the potential to affect both the mediator and the outcome of the trial. Failure to account for such potentially confounding factors has the potential to supply findings for biased mediation analysis (Emsley et al. 2010; MacKinnon, 2008). This problem has been highlighted by Judd & Kenny (1981) in earlier and less often cited work and can be addressed at least in part by evaluating confounders and adding them to regression models. Judd and Kenny (1981)

Another issue brought to light in both the Baron and Kenny papers and the Judd and Kenny papers (Baron and Kenny, 1986; Judd and Kenny, 1981) was measurement error in variables, which can lead to biased effect estimates. These articles were published in 1986 and 1981, respectively. The issue of measurement inaccuracy is likely to be of relevance in the fields of psychology and psychiatry, as we often deal with unobservable or hidden features. Using structural equation modeling (SEM), it is possible to model the connections that exist between underlying latent property variables, where each variable is quantified by a set of scale items or measures. For example, maladaptive cognitions can be evaluated through a questionnaire having various questions that may be indicative of such cognitions ("I am not well", "They strongly believe I cannot do this", etc.). Another method of measuring maladaptive cognitions is observation. In this case, the latent trait is dysfunctional ways of thinking. Because SEM models latent variables and uses many items or measures, it can account for measurement error and highlight correlations between latent features (Bollen and Pearl, 2013; MacKinnon, 2008). Path analysis models are a type of SEM that uses only previously observed variables (MacKinnon, 2008).

4. Mechanical Processes of Psychotherapies

Although more research has been done on the mechanistic processes of psychotherapies recently, there is still a lack of information in the literature. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (Maric et al, 2013; Odoni et al, 2013; Turner et al, 2007; Whisman, 1993) and mindfulness-based therapies

(MBTs) (Branstrom et al, 2010; Coffey & Hartman, 2008; Sears & Kraus, 2009) are two examples of psychotherapy that have been heavily mediated.

Evaluation of theoretically relevant process variables is one of the most common applications of mediation analysis in practice. This has the potential to improve therapeutic techniques as well as theoretical frameworks. CBT is an example of a treatment for which mechanism evaluation is particularly necessary as it is now often used transdiagnostically. This makes CBT an excellent candidate for further research. The goal of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is to change negative habits of thinking and acting that are thought to cause and/or perpetuate symptoms and impairment in a wide range of diseases. The CBRT needs to do this. It is thought that cognition and behavior have a key role in the transformation process at a large level. In the context of chronic pain (Turner et al. 2007), panic disorder (Hofmann et al., 2007), chronic fatigue syndrome (Chalder et al., 2015; Moss-Morris et al., 2005; Stahl et al.), (2014) and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) (Lackner et al., 2007; Miklowitz & Scott, 2009; Reme et al., 2011), (Hofmann et al., 2012).

depression (Beck et al . 1987), medically unexplained symptoms (Deary et al., 2007), and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) have been the focus of development of specific CBT models (Toner et al., 2000). These models supply a basis on which empirical research can be conducted, making it possible to confirm and further develop the models. For example, in the case of irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), the cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) paradigm postulates that reduced symptom intensity and impact on life can be attributed to treatment-induced changes in the conceptualization of bowel symptoms (Toner et al. two thousand). Changes in views that IBS is an uncontrollable medical disease and increases in behavior patterns in the face of symptoms should be included as part of this reconceptualization. A study examining cognitive and behavioral factors in IBS specifically found evidence to support this (Reme et al. 2011).

5. Change in Cognition as well as Behavior

According to the findings of the study, a change in the cognition as well as the behavior of the person mediated the decrease in the intensity of the symptoms and the effect on the life. Because

the inferred temporal ordering was not integrated into the design of the trial, studies with simultaneous mediator and outcome measures are likely to supply less convincing evidence for therapeutic mechanisms. In this case, the rationale for this decision was that there was no significant added change in mediator variables evaluated at later time points, and as a result, the inclusion of scores from later time points in the analysis made slight difference. However, from a theoretical point of view it is preferable to construct the research to fit the intended chronological order. Therefore, research should try to include mediators evaluated at time points that occur before the outcome variable. More attention will be paid to this in the future.

6. A Detailed Look at the Mediation Mechanism

therapies within the same school of psychotherapy differs, to clarify the extent to which different processes cause changes in outcomes. For example, when applied to irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) in cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), different researchers suggest the importance of different mechanical processes. These processes involve a change in cognitions and/or behavior as opposed to a reduction in distress and anxiety. Results favoring one important process over another have been inconsistent up to this point. Lackner et al. (2007) and Jones et al. conducted a separate study on the effects of mediation on CBT for irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), and conflicting findings are evidence of this point (2011). Both studies looked at the possible roles that psychological distress might play in mediating the effects of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) on IBS outcomes, but they came to conflicting conclusions. However, each of these studies and the comparison between them had several obvious shortcomings that needed to be addressed. Jones et al. They used the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale as a measure of anxiety and depression (Snaith, 2003, Lackner et al.)

In their study, they used the Brief Symptom Inventory as a measure of psychological distress. First, the two studies used different tools to assess their participants' levels of psychological distress (Derogatis & Spencer, 1993). Lackner et al. He evaluated a theory-informed mediation model as opposed to the explicit and theory-informed mediation model proposed by Jones et al. He chose the road model developed by Jones et al. Its variants were arranged according to a sequence

informed by an interpretation of the Biopsychosocial model (Drossman, 1998), according to which CBT had a positive effect on mood by reducing anxiety and depression, resulting in a reduction in bowel symptoms. In contrast, Lackner et al. evaluated a complex road model with no clear theoretically informed structure. According to this model, there were three direct pathways from CBT to all three outcomes (quality of life, overall symptom improvement, and distress) and multiple indirect pathways across various outcome measures.

7. Cognitions Greatly Influence Therapy's Impact on the Intensity of Symptoms

According to the findings of Jones and colleagues, anxiety and, to a lesser extent, depression had a mediating effect, meaning that reductions in both factors led to less severe manifestations of symptoms. On the other hand, Lackner and colleagues found no evidence that psychological distress plays a significant role in the mediation process. Instead, they discovered that CBT had a direct effect on the intensity of symptoms while unrelated to distress. Lackner et al. This is reinforced by more recent mediation work, which also shows that distress is not a significant mediator in the relationship (Chilcot & Moss-Morris, 2013). This study measured both cognitions and behaviors, and the researchers concluded that cognitions influenced the effect of therapy on the intensity of symptoms. This lends more credence to the cognitive behavioral model of irritable bowel syndrome since the change in outcome is due to cognitions and not discomfort.

The studies conducted by Jones and Lackner supply a sample of a few of the limitations of current research on mediation:

- (a) Outcomes will be decided by the mediation factors included in the analysis. It is essential that the field of mediation studies is well informed by theory to ease the investigation of all potential mediators as required by the conceptual framework.*
- (b) It is possible to use different measures to evaluate the same or comparable concepts, which may limit interpretation between studies. An example of this would be a measure of anxiety as opposed to a measure of psychological distress.*

- (c) *Results may be affected by the mediation analysis method used. This will be considered in a later part of the article and*
- (d) *It is possible to have a longer mediation chain with more than one mediating variable in the causal pathway, where a mediator may serve to mediate the effects of a mediator (Taylor et al. 2008). (“Establishing how psychological therapies work: the importance of ...”) In this example, this happens when a change in the person's cognitions mediates a change in the person's psychological distress, which explains a change in the person's symptom severity.*

8. Putting the Hypothesis together

The use of mediation studies as an approach to research processes guided by psychological theory has been discussed in the earlier section. Awareness exploration supplies a window of opportunity to explore the use of backtranslation. Although the delivery of MBT is expanding among various therapeutic groups, the theoretical foundations of this type of therapy are still inadequate. In 2006, a preliminary theory was presented, hypothesizing that mindfulness practice can have positive therapeutic consequences (Shapiro et al. 2006). The theory suggested that changes in self-regulation, values, resilience (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral), and exposure to internal processes may function as mechanisms responsible for outcomes such as a reduction in symptoms or distress. These four variables were defined as changes in self-regulation, values, resilience (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral), and exposure to internal processes. It has been suggested that greater "reperception" and "decentralization" are how these processes can be conducted. These aspects relate to one's ability to take an objective stance towards one's experiences.

9. Absence, Resensing, and Decentralization

Carmody et al. (2009) put this idea to the test by applying the causal stages method to mediation in their research. This research has several methodological concerns that need to be considered and these issues should be considered. Initially, participants were not randomly assigned to diverse

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groups, meaning that the study was conducted without the use of a control or comparison group. Second, many of the measurements lacked the previously proved reliability and validity. The authors produced a joint holistic measure of awareness, re-perception, and decentralization; Variables that were considered separately in the theoretical model given by Shapiro et al. Some of these measures were further adjusted before they were later included in the mediation study (2006). The study was conducted using the Baron & Kenny causal stages technique, despite the limitations discussed earlier in this article. Finally, the authors did not include any measurements that were evaluated over multiple periods over time, which further reduced the likelihood of reaching a causal conclusion.

The findings of the study showed that the effects of compound mindfulness and re-perception on psychological symptoms were partially mediated by two of the four processes described in the model. These two processes are clarification of values and cognitive, emotional, and behavioral flexibility. Rather than supplying conclusive evidence for the hypotheses proposed by Shapiro et al. the results served as a basis for focusing further research. (“Full article: Establishing how psychological therapies work: the ...”) Additionally, the results highlighted the possibility that there may be other mediation processes not accounted for in the model.

Further research on important awareness processes such as cognitive and behavioral flexibility is based on both theory and empirical work (Baer, 2010; Heeren et al. 2009; Holzel et al., 2011; Kuyken et al., 2010). . (Baer, 2010; Heeren et al. 2009; Holzel et al., 2011; Kuyken et al., 2010) Elements such as self-understanding, which are closely related to and included in the model (Baer et al., 2012; Hayes et al., 2004) ; McCracken and Velleman, 2010; Neff, 2003; Petrocchi et al., 2014) continued to attract research focusing on the study of the mechanisms of MBTs (Baer, 2010; Holzel et al., 2011; Kuyken, most recently, in various clinical studies of MBTs). A comprehensive review of empirical research evaluating mechanisms on outcomes found certain critical processes. Coping mechanisms included cognitive reactivity, experiential avoidance, emotional control, and self-compassion. The accumulation of empirical veri of such processes will guide both broader and refined models. will continue to generate cumulative insights (Bullock et al. 2010).

10. Conclusion

Exploring mediation within the framework of psychotherapy is important for several reasons, one of which is to shed light on processes prevalent across various psychotherapeutic modalities. Transdiagnostic conceptualization of more common diseases and treatment modalities (Newby et al. 2015) is beyond the scope of this article as it is beyond the scope of what is discussed here. However, the finding of beneficial mechanistic processes that expand across therapeutic strategies and diagnoses could make it possible to develop more joint therapies that are successful for a wide variety of outcomes. Much more work is needed in the literature on this subject.

11. References

- A network meta-analysis of the effects of psychotherapies, pharmacotherapies, and their combination in the treatment of adult depression. *World Psychiatry*. 2020; 19: 92-107
- Allen M, Bromley A, Kuyken W, Sonnenberg SJ. Participants' experiences of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy: it changed me in about every way possible. *Behav Cogn Psychother*. 2009;37:413–30.
- Barnes M, Sherlock S, Thomas L, Kessler D, Kuyken W, Owen-Smith A, et al. No pain, no gain: depressed clients' experiences of cognitive behavioral therapy. *BrJ Clin Psychol*. 2013;52:347–64.
- Beattie A, Shaw A, Kaur S, Kessler D. Primary-care patients' expectations, and experiences of online cognitive behavioral therapy for depression: a qualitative study. *Health Expectation*. 2009;12:45–59.
- Bendelin N, Hesser H, Dahl J, Carlbring P, Nelson KZ, Andersson G. Experiences of guided internet-based cognitive-behavioural treatment for depression: a qualitative study. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2011;11.
- Boggs JM, Beck A, Felder JN, Dimidjian S, Metcalf CA, Segal ZV, et al. Web-based intervention in mindfulness meditation for reducing residual depressive symptoms and relapse prophylaxis: a qualitative study. (“Reducing Residual Depressive Symptoms With Web-based Mindful Mood ...”) (“Reducing Residual Depressive Symptoms with Web-based Mindful Mood ...”) *J Med Internet Res*. 2014;16:e87.
- CASP Checklist: ten questions to help you make sense of qualitative research. (“CASP-Qualitative-Checklist-2018.pdf - Course Hero”) 2018. <https://casp-uk.net/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/CASP->

- Qualitative-Checklist-2018_fillable_form.pdf.
- Choi NG, Wilson NL, Sirrianni L, Marinucci ML, Hegel MT. Acceptance of home-based telehealth problem-solving therapy for depressed, low-income homebound older adults: qualitative interviews with the participants and aging-service case managers. *gerontologist* 2014;54:704–13.
- Cramer H, Salisbury C, Conrad J, Eldred J, Araya R. Group cognitive behavioral therapy for women with depression: pilot and feasibility study for a randomized controlled trial using mixed methods. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2011;11.
- Cuijpers P Cristea IA Karyotaki E Reijnders M Hollon SD, Part studies of psychological treatments of adult depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychother Res*. 2019; 29: 15-29
- Cuijpers P Karyotaki E Reijnders M Purgato M Barbui C, Psychotherapies for depression in low- and middle-income countries: a meta-analysis. *World Psychiatry*. 2018; 17: 90-101
- Cuijpers P Noma H Karyotaki E Vinkers CH Cipriani a Furukawa TA (“A network meta-analysis of the effects of psychotherapies ...”) (“A network meta-analysis of the effects of psychotherapies ...”)
- Donohue JM, Cevasco M, Rosenthal MB. A decade of direct-to-consumer advertising of prescription drugs. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2007;357(7):673–681.
- Druss BG. The changing face of US mental health care. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2010;167:1491–1421.
- Duffy M, Gillespie K, Clark DM. Post-traumatic stress disorder in the context of terrorism and ther civil conflict in Northern Ireland: randomized controlled trial. *BMJ: British Medical Journal*. 2007;334(7604):1147. [PMC free article]
- "Eftekhari A, Ruzek JI, Crowley JJ, Rosen CS, Greenbaum MA, Karlin BE." (“Reducing suicidal ideation through evidence-based treatment for ...”) (“Reducing suicidal ideation through evidence-based treatment for ...”) Effectiveness of national implementation of prolonged exposure therapy in Veterans Affairs care. *JAMA psychiatry*. 2013;70(9):949–955.
- "Egan SJ, Wade TD, Shafran R. Perfectionism as a transdiagnostic process: A clinical review." (“Guided Web-Based Cognitive Behavior Therapy for Perfectionism: Results ...”) (“Guided Web-Based Cognitive Behavior Therapy for Perfectionism: Results ...”) *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2011;31(2):203–212.
- Ehlers A, Clark DM, Hackmann A, McManus F, Fennell M, Herbert C, et al. A randomized controlled trial of cognitive therapy, a self-help booklet, and repeated assessments as early

- interventions for posttraumatic stress disorder. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2003;60:1024–1032.
- Ehlers A, Clark DM. A cognitive model of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Behavior Research and Therapy*. 2000;38:319–345 .
- "Ehlers A, Hackmann A, Steil R, Clohessy S, Wenninger K, Winter H. The nature of intrusive memories after trauma: The warning signal hypothesis." ("The nature of intrusive memories after trauma: the warning signal ...") ("Sex differences in intrusive memories following trauma - PLOS") *Behaviour Research and Therapy*. 2002;40:995–1002.
- "Ellard KK, Deckersbach T, Sylvia LG, Nierenberg AA, Barlow DH." ("Kristen Ellard - Division of Neuropsychiatry and Neuromodulation") ("Kristen Ellard - Division of Neuropsychiatry and Neuromodulation") *Transdiagnostic treatment of bipolar disorder and comorbid anxiety with the unified protocol: A clinical replication series. Behavior Modification*. 2012;36(4):482–508. [PMC free article]
- Essau, CA, Conradt, J., & Petermann, F. (two thousand). Frequency, comorbidity, and psychosocial impairment of anxiety disorders in German adolescents. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 14(3), 263–279.
- Fairburn CG, Cooper Z, Doll HA, O'Connor ME, Bohn K, Hawker DM, et al. Transdiagnostic cognitive-behavioral therapy for patients with eating disorders: a two-site trial with 60-week follow-up. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2009;166(3):311. [PMC free article]
- Fairburn CG, Cooper Z, Shafran R. Cognitive behavior therapy for eating disorders: a "transdiagnostic" theory and treatment. *Behavior Research and Therapy*. 2003;41:509–528.
- Farchione TJ, Fairholme CP, Ellard KK, Boisseau CL, Thompson-Hollands J, Carl JR, et al. Unified protocol for transdiagnostic treatment of emotional disorders: a randomized controlled trial. *Behavior Therapy*. 2012;43(3):666–678. [PMC free article]
- Fathi A, Renner W, Juen B. A qualitative study of cognitive-behavioral therapy for Iranian migrants with mild/moderate depression in Austria. *Bull Menn Clin*. 2016;80:166–86.
- Feldman S. The 'millionaires tax' and mental health policy in California. *Health Affairs*. 2009;28(3):809–815.
- Fisher, Z., & Tipton, E. (2015). *Robumeta: An R-package for robust variance estimation in meta-analysis*. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1503.02220>.
- "Fraire MG, Ollendick TH. Anxiety and oppositional defiant disorder: A transdiagnostic conceptualization." ("Thomas H. Ollendick - Publications - Neurotree") ("Thomas H. Ollendick

- Publications - Neurotree") Clinical Psychology Review. 2013;33(2):229–240.
- Ganella, DE, & Kim, JH (2014). "Developmental rodent models of fear and anxiety: From neurobiology to pharmacology." ("Tinbergen's challenge for the neuroscience of behavior - PMC") ("Developmental rodent models of fear and anxiety: from ... - CORE") British Journal of Pharmacology, 171(20), 4556–4574.
- Garfield RL, Zuvekas SH, Lave JR, Donohue JM. The impact of national health care reform on adults with severe mental disorders. American Journal of Psychiatry. 2011;168(5):486–494.
- Gaudio BA, Miller IW. The evidence-based practice of psychotherapy: Facing the challenges that lie ahead. Clinical Psychology Review. 2013;33(7):813–824 .
- "Geers AL, Rose JP, Fowler SL, Rasinski HM, Brown JA, Helfer SG." ("Should treatment for depression be based more on patient preference?") ("Should treatment for depression be based more on patient preference?") Why does choice enhance treatment effectiveness? Using placebo treatments to prove the role of personal control. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology. 2013;105:549–566.
- Gillespie K, Duffy M, Hackmann A, Clark DM. Community-based cognitive therapy in the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder following the Omagh bomb. Behavior Research and Therapy. 2002;40:345–357.
- Ginsburg, GS, & Drake, KL (2002). School-based treatment for anxious African American adolescents: A controlled pilot study. Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry, 41(7), 768–775.
- Glasman D, Finlay WML, Brock D. Becoming a self-therapist: using cognitive-behavioural therapy for recurrent depression and/or dysthymia after completing therapy. Psychol Psychother Theory Res Pract. 2004;77:335–51.
- Glenn D, Golinelli D, Rose RD, Roy-Byrne P, Stein MB, Sullivan G, et al. Who gets the most out of cognitive behavioral therapy for anxiety disorders? The role of treatment dose and patient engagement. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology. 2013;81(4):639–649. [PMC free article]
- "Goldman W. Economic grand rounds: Is there a shortage of psychiatrists?" ("Operational Lessons from a Large Accountable Care Organization") ("Operational Lessons from a Large Accountable Care Organization") Psychiatric Services. 2001;52(12):1587–1589.
- Grant BF, Goldstein RB, Chou SP, Huang B, Stinson FS, Dawson DA, et al. Sociodemographic and psychopathologic predictors of first incidence of DSM-IV substance use, mood and anxiety disorders: results

- from the Wave 2 National Epidemiologic Survey on Alcohol and Related Conditions. *Molecular Psychiatry*. 2008;14(11):1051–1066. [PMC free article]
- Gyani A, Shafran R, Layard R, Clark DM. Enhancing recovery rates: lessons from year one of IAPT. *Behavior Research and Therapy*. 2013;51(9):597–606. [PMC free article]
- "Hannes K, Macaitis K. A move to more systematic and transparent approaches in qualitative evidence synthesis: update on a review of published papers." ("A move to more systematic and transparent approaches in ... - Research") ("Patients' experiences of chronic non-malignant musculoskeletal pain: a ...") *Qual Res*. 2012;12:402–42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794111432992>.
- Hansen NB, Lambert MJ. An evaluation of the dose, response relationship in naturalistic treatment settings using survival analysis. *Mental Health Services Research*. 2003;5(1):1–12 .
- Hayward, C., Varady, S., Albano, AM, Thienemann, M., Henderson, L., & Schatzberg, AF (two thousand). Cognitive-behavioral group therapy for social phobia in female adolescents: Results of a pilot study. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 39(6), 721–726.
- Hedges, LV, Tipton, E., & Johnson, MC (2010). "Robust variance estimation in meta-regression with dependent effect size estimates." ("Robust variance estimation in meta-regression with dependent ... - PubMed") ("Robust variance estimation in meta-regression with dependent ... - PubMed") *Research Synthesis Methods*, 1(1), 39–65.
- Herbert, JD, Gaudiano, BA, Rheingold, AA, Moitra, E., Myers, VH, Dalrymple, KL, & Brandsma, LL (2009). ("A disorder-specific group cognitive behavior therapy for social anxiety ...") *Cognitive behavior therapy for generalized social anxiety disorder in adolescents: A randomized controlled trial. Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 23(2), 167–177.
- Higgins, JPT, & Green, S. (2011). *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions (Vol. 4)*. Wiley.
- Higgins, JPT, Altman, DG, Gøtzsche, PC, Jüni, P., Moher, D., Oxman, AD, Savović, J., Schulz, KF, Weeks, L., & Sterne, JA (2011). ("Complementary and Alternative Medicine for Postoperative Pain - LWW") *The cochrane collaboration's tool for assessing risk of bias in randomized trials.* ("The Cochrane Collaboration's tool for assessing risk of bias in ...") ("The Cochrane Collaboration's tool for assessing risk of bias in ...") *BMJ*, 343, d5928.
- Higgins, JPT, Thompson, SG, Deeks, JJ, & Altman, DG (2003). *Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. BMJ*,

- 327(7414), 557–560.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557>
- Hudson, JL, Keers, R., Roberts, S., Coleman, JRI, Breen, G., Arendt, K., Bögels, S., Cooper, P., Creswell, C., Hartman, C., Heiervang, ER, & Hartman, C. (2015). Clinical predictors of response to cognitive-behavioral therapy in pediatric anxiety disorders: The genes for treatment (GxT) study. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 54(6), 454–463.
- Hudson, JL, Kendall, PC, Coles, ME, Robin, JA, & Webb, A. (2002). "The other side of the coin: Using intervention research in child anxiety disorders to inform developmental psychopathology." ("Parents' perception of child and adolescent mental health problems and ...") ("The other side of the coin: Using intervention research in child ...") *Development and Psychopathology*, 14(4), 819–841.
- Ingul, JM, Aune, T., & Nordahl, HM (2014). A randomized controlled trial of individual cognitive therapy, group cognitive behavior therapy and attentional placebo for adolescent social phobia. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*, 83(1), 54–61. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000354672>
- James, AC, James, G., Cowdrey, FA, Soler, A., & Choke, A. (2015). Cognitive behavioral therapy for anxiety disorders in children and adolescents. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004690.pub4>
- James, AC, Reardon, T., Soler, A., James, G., & Creswell, C. (2020). Cognitive behavioral therapy for anxiety disorders in children and adolescents. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD013162.pub2>
- Lindhiem O Bennett CB Trentacosta CJ McLear C Client preferences affect treatment satisfaction, completion, and clinical outcome: a meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev*. 2014; 34: 506-517
- McHugh RK Whitton SW Peckham AD Welge JA Otto MW, Patient preference for psychological vs pharmacologic treatment of psychiatric disorders: a meta-analytic review. *J Clin Psychiatry*. 2013; 74: 595-602
- Olfson M Blanco C Marcus SC, Treatment of adult depression in the United States. *JAMA Intern Med*. 2016; 176: 1482-1491
- Saver BG, Van-Nguyen V, Keppel G, Doescher MP. A qualitative study of depression in primary care: missed opportunities for diagnosis and education. *J Am Board Fam Med*. 2007;20:28–35.
<https://doi.org/10.3122/jabfm.2007.01.060026>.

Van Ginneken N Chin WY Lim YC et al.,
Primary-level worker interventions
for the care of people living with
mental disorders and distress in low-
and middle-income countries.
("Psychosocial treatment outcomes

of common mental disorders vary
widely ...") ("Psychosocial treatment
outcomes of common mental
disorders vary widely ...") Cochrane
Database Syst Rev. 2021;
8CD009149